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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION (WTO): TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS FOR NIGERIA

By

Umar Abubakar Dubagari,* Muhammad Waje Bawa**

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Abstract

The growth in volumes of trade and services due, in part, to information technology (IT) revolution that resulted in the formulation of new global trade rules over the past two decades meant that the world economy has undergone tremendous changes. However, there are growing concerns about the future of Nigeria, as a member of the World Trade Organization (WTO) that lacked the basic necessary impetus to adequately compete in an increasingly challenging global economic setting. Adopting the doctrinal research methodology, this paper argued that the WTO's principles of non-discrimination relegate Nigeria to a mere appendage struggling to secure substantial benefits from the global trading regime that, for all intents and purposes, has shown to be extremely unbalanced and disadvantageous to it. The paper also argued that the global trade competitiveness of Nigeria remains a major challenge due to high poverty rate, high profile corruption, political instability, poor regulatory and institutional frameworks that would spur economic development. The paper further argued that dependence on financial aids from developed countries, trade barriers and other forms of protectionist policies that characterized developing countries are confronting issues that hinders Nigeria the potential benefits of trade multilateralism. The paper concluded that although the WTO has the potentials of becoming a powerful tool for global trade integration and for it to justify the claim of advocating for the welfares of all its members, the need for reform of its policies that will accommodate Nigeria's informal sectors, as a developing economy is not only desirable, but compelling.

Keywords: Legal Framework, Establishment, WTO, Trends, Challenges, Prospects, Nigeria

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The US agenda is “liberalization if it benefits me, protectionism. if it benefits me, what counts is my commercial interest.” - Martin Khor

The commencement of operations by the World Trade Organization (WTO) after its establishment in 1995 marked the major transformation in the development of global trade since the aftermath of the Second World War. As the largest global trade institution, the WTO regulate trade in goods,¹ services,² and intellectual property (IP)³ between member countries by providing the legal and institutional frameworks for trade negotiations with the aim of enforcing members’ adherence to its agreements.⁴ The set of agreements that accompanied the establishment of the WTO are General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT), General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS), Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPs), Agreement on Subsidies and Countervailing Measures (ASCM), Trade Related Investment Measures (TRIMS), Agreement on Import Licensing Procedures (AILP), etc. It also introduced an Annex on dispute settlement referred to as the Rules and Procedures Governing the Disputes Settlement Understanding (DSU), which was a considerable departure from the dispute settlement procedures under the old GATT. The WTO is committed to better standards of living, employment opportunities, sustainable development for all member countries, and improved stake for developing countries and least developed countries (LDCs) in the global trade.⁵

The WTO has the potentials of becoming an influential instrument in the international trading system beside the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank, with regards to the preservation of harmonious international trade relations through its trade policy review mechanisms (TPRM), trade disputes settlement devices and sanctions, rather than trade destructive and destabilizing transactions that will

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¹ This includes agriculture, product standards, subsidies, and anti-dumping, etc.

² This includes banks, insurance firms, telecommunication companies, etc.

³ This includes copyrights, patents, trademarks, geographical indications, industrial designs, integrated circuit, etc.

⁴ Adetokunbo Kayode., ‘Re – Assessing Nigeria, WTO on the Benefits Scale’, 2017, <<https://leadership.ng/2017/12/11/re-assessing-nigeria-wto-benefits-scale/>> accessed 6 October 2023.

⁵ Baldwin, Richard, ‘The World Trade Organization and the Future of Multilateralism’ *Journal of Economic Perspectives* (2016) (30) (1) 95.

escalate to wars.⁶ However, there is an improvement in the WTO disputes settlement processes, but Nigeria's participation in the process is negligible, due to its inconsequential involvement in global trade.⁷

At the 13th Ministerial Conference of the WTO,⁸ Nigeria declared its readiness to actively contribute to global dialogue and negotiations, with a commitment to fostering international trade, cooperation, and inclusivity, as it looks forward to positive implementation of the MC13 resolutions. The Conference updated the WTO's agreements on trade policy, reviewed the functions of the multilateral trading system, and defined the agenda for the WTO's future work. Therefore, the Conference presents a crucial opportunity for Nigeria to participate in negotiations for, among other issues, Special and Differential Treatment (SDT) that developing country members and LDCs can receive in trade agreements, including discussions on both the environment and inclusivity in trade policy that will impact on Nigeria's future in the global trade.⁹

While Nigeria continues to grapple with the economic fallout of the COVID-19 pandemic and seeks collective solutions for sustainable development, digital trade and food security continue to stand out as top priorities. Nigeria's participation at the conference will pave the way for it to achieve concrete positive outcomes in the WTO agriculture trade reforms negotiations which should be approached from a food security and livelihood perspective. Nigeria calls for the continued review of the trading rules for agriculture with a view to achieving equitable rules that enhance food security, by providing the necessary policy space for augmenting production and productivity and protecting livelihoods, along with diversifying and stabilising the global supply of food products by achieving reductions in inequitable trade-distorting subsidies.¹⁰

Regarding Digital Trade, Nigeria argued for the E-Commerce Work Programme and Moratorium to be approached from a development perspective. This will enable it to explore the appropriate policy instruments within the WTO toolbox that can foster the development of e-commerce ecosystems in the country and hoping that issues

⁶ Malenbakeng Agnes Forere, 'The Relationship of the WTO Law and Regional Trade Agreements in Dispute Settlement: From Fragmentation to Coherence' *Global Trade Law Series* (2016) (50) 41.

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ Held in Abu Dhabi, UAE from February 26 – 29, 2024.

⁹ Doris Uzoka-Anite, 'Nigeria Wants Positive Outcomes at WTO Conference' *Punch Newspaper* 26 February 2024 <<https://punchng.com/nigeria-wants-positive-outcomes-at-wto-conference/>> accessed 17 August 2024

¹⁰ Ibid.

regarding the scope and the definition of the moratorium be clarified so that it can understand the scope of its commitment.¹¹

Although the WTO has remained at the forefront of promoting trade liberalization amongst member nations since it came on board, the journey so far has not been reassuring for Nigeria as the system indicates that the WTO is primarily concerned with the potential benefits of developed countries at the expense of Nigeria, and this raises a lot of concerns regarding the future direction of the WTO.¹²

2.0 TRENDS

2.1 Objectives of the World Trade Organization

The aim of the WTO is to guarantee that trade moves as efficiently, predictably, and freely as possible.¹³ Among other things, the objectives of the WTO are as follows:

- i. improve the living standards of people in the WTO member countries.
- ii. guarantee job opportunities for people in the WTO member countries.
- iii. intensify manufacturing and trade of goods of member countries.
- iv. intensify trade of services of member countries.
- v. safeguard the best use of world properties.
- vi. defend the environment and introduce sustainable development, so that development and environment can go together.¹⁴
- vii. ensure that developing countries and LDCs members secure a better transaction in the global trade.¹⁵

Essentially, the WTO seeks to eradicate structural inequalities in multidimensional trading system and serve as an unbiased intermediary for countries to negotiate. Thus, apart from been home to developed economies, the WTO also accommodate developing countries with unstable economic conditions, yet very attractive. The purpose is to create an equitable trading environment for goods and services,¹⁶ among member countries, irrespective of their level of economic development.

2.2 Functions of the World Trade Organization

¹¹ Ibid.

¹² Kwa Aileen, 'WTO and Developing Countries' <https://ips-dc.org/wto_and_developing_countries/> accessed 30 November 2023.

¹³ Ibid.

¹⁴ Article III

¹⁵ Pini Davide, 'The WTO's Role in the World Economy: A Unique Chance to Achieve Corporate Responsibility' International Development Programme (2015) 4.

¹⁶ Ayres Thomas Banwell, 'The Role of the WTO in Assisting Developing Countries, Especially the BRICS: An Analysis of Doha and Bali' International Immersion Programme Paper (2015) (3) (1)

The WTO performs the following functions:

- i. implement the guidelines and requirements associated with TPRM.
- ii. provide the medium for members to decide the future policies associated with trade and tariffs.
- iii. provide provisions for the application of multilateral and bilateral agreements of global trade.
- iv. administer the rules and procedures that relate to dispute settlement.¹⁷
- v. assist the IMF and the World Bank to establish a coherent universal economic policy.

The function of the WTO includes the application of its agreements, technical assistance, and improve the involvement of developing countries and LDCs in the multilateral trading arrangement. It also encourages consultations and collaborations with International NonGovernmental Organizations (INGOs), whose responsibilities relates to those of the WTO.¹⁸ The WTO is basically responsible for the administration of all agreements relating to series of economic issues, such as trade in goods, trade in services, investments, import licensing procedures, subsidies, and intellectual property rights (IPRs), etc.¹⁹ Thus, it has wittingly administered a dispute settlement mechanism²⁰ and achieved periodic trade review policies.²¹

2.3 Principles of Non-Discrimination and Reciprocity

The WTO agreement is anchored on two main principles; non-discrimination²² and reciprocity and the two components of the principles are the Most-Favored-Nation (MFN)²³ and National Treatment (NT) rules.²⁴ MFN requires that a concession afforded by a member of the WTO to another member must be afforded to every other member, with certain exceptions allowed to regional trade agreements (RTA), preferential treatment for developing countries and LDCs, and an existing member

¹⁷Smriti Chand, 'World Trade Organization (WTO): Objectives and Functions' <<https://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/trade-2/world-trade-organization-wto-objectives-and-functions/23529>> accessed 27 November 2023.

¹⁸Walid Doudech, 'World Trade Organization (WTO)' <<https://sites.google.com/site/walidabduhrahim/home/my-studies-in-english/27-world-trade-organization-wto>> accessed on 13 May 2023.

¹⁹ MN Shaw, *International Law* (4th Edn, Grotius Press Ltd 1997) 893.

²⁰ Annex 2 to the Agreement establishing the WTO.

²¹ Annex 3 to the Agreement establishing the WTO.

²² Each member country is guaranteed that its exportations will be treated with fairness in other members' markets.

²³ Article I of the Original GATT.

²⁴ Part II of the Original GATT Agreement.

invoking a non-application clause against a newly assenting member. The NT on the other hand, requires WTO members to indulge foreign goods with all the privileges of domestically produced goods. However, the protocol of provisional application allows member countries to avoid NT as a general obligation in all areas, except trade in services.²⁵

The second principle that underlies all WTO Agreements is reciprocity that restricts free riding, otherwise, it may be abused on the grounds of non-discrimination principle. It allows the granting of common reductions in tariff rates, quotas, or other trade limitations. It also makes the procedure of granting tariff reductions diplomatically practicable, thus, these reductions in tariff are not expected to be of general application to other member countries with which the contracting parties have trade dealings.²⁶ The system also allows developing countries some degree of flexibilities in the implementation of their commitments to the agreements.²⁷

The WTO also relies on accountability, enforcement of obligations, and the existence of protection measures that allow member countries to control trade under certain conditions. A member is not only expected to circulate its trade guidelines to other members and notify the WTO of any impeding deviations, but its trade policies are subjected to examination by the WTO through the TPRM. Thus, where a member country default on its obligations, that country can be sanctioned by the WTO.²⁸

2.4 Structure of the World Trade Organization

The WTO Secretariat located in Geneva, Switzerland is headed by a Director-General and comprises of a multi-ethnic team of highly-qualified persons with wide range of skills, knowledge and experience that serve with professionalism, objectivity, and honesty. Among others, the Secretariat is responsible for; assisting the WTO member countries with their trade negotiations and implementation of the agreements, providing technical assistance to developing countries and LDCs, providing trade performance and trade policy evaluations, and resolving trade disagreements relating to clarification of WTO guidelines and precedents.²⁹

²⁵ A Narlikar, *The World Trade Organization: A Very Short Introduction* (Oxford University Press, 2005) 28.

²⁶ Equal treatment is fair only among peers, a weakling cannot shoulder the burden of a giant.'

²⁷ Smriti Chand, (n. 13)

²⁸ A Narlikar, (n. 21), 31.

²⁹ Article VI

The Agreement³⁰ establishing WTO provides that:

- i. “There shall be a Secretariat of the WTO (hereinafter referred to as the Secretariat) headed by a Director-General.
- ii. The Ministerial Conference shall appoint the Director-General and adopt regulations setting out the powers, duties, Conditions of Service, and term of office of the Director-General.
- iii. The Director-General shall appoint the members of the staff of the Secretariat and determine their duties and Conditions of Service in accordance with regulations adopted by the Ministerial Conference.
- iv. The responsibilities of the Director-General and of the staff of the Secretariat shall be exclusively international in character. In the discharge of their duties, the Director-General and the staff of the Secretariat shall not seek or accept instructions from any government or any other authority external to the WTO. They shall refrain from any action which might adversely reflect on their position as international bureaucrats.
- v. The Members of the WTO shall respect the international character of the responsibilities of the Director-General and of the staff of the Secretariat and shall not seek to influence them in the discharge of their duties.”

In summary, the main duties of the Secretariat, among others, are the provisions of technical assistance to several councils and committees as may be constituted and the ministerial conferences, provides technical support for developing countries and LDCs, evaluates global trade and inform the public and media on WTO’s affairs. It also provides legal support in the trade dispute settlement procedure and counsels potential members of the WTO.

However, the Secretariat neither has the *locus standi* to bring legal proceedings against member countries that breaches the WTO Agreements, nor the power to sanction erring members. Rather, it is governments of member states that can enforce WTO rules by lodging formal complaints against other governments through the Dispute Settlement Understanding (DSU). The process is considered very symbolic because it has distributional effects at both domestic and international levels.³¹

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ US leather exporters gained market access to Japan, when it removed quantitative restrictions following a GATT panel ruling in 1983 in favour of the US.

2.5 WTO Decision Making Body

As a multilateral trade governing body, the WTO has three arms of power: administrative, lawmaking, and adjudicatory bodies, which makes it an exceptional international organization amongst its peers. The Ministerial Conference, which consists of the representatives of all members, who usually meet, at least once every two years and exercise the functions of the Conference between sessions is the highest-level decision-making body of the WTO.³² However, decision-making in the WTO is mostly informal and behind closed doors, usually at the green room with few members in attendance. Decisions are made by way of consensus and such consensus becomes binding on the rest of the members. Although there is the possibility of a majority vote in decision making process, but it has never been put into practice and was infrequently used under the GATT, the predecessor of the WTO.³³

The next in line after the Ministerial Conference is the General Council, which consists of ambassadors and heads of delegation who resides in Geneva, but more often representatives are sent from member countries' capital cities, and which hold meetings several times in a year at the WTO Headquarters. The General Council also acts in both capacities of the TPRB and the disputes settlement body (DSB). The main ambition of the DSB is to afford safety and certainty to the multilateral trading system that may be obstructed by other dispute settlement mechanisms available in RTA that may run parallel with the DSB.³⁴

Below the General Council, there are also Council for Trade in Goods, Council for Trade in Services and Council for TRIPs, etc.³⁵ In addition, there are several other specialized commissions, working groups and parties responsible for distinct agreements in other areas such as the environment, development, and membership requests and ascension.³⁶

2.6 Trade Policy Review Mechanism (TPRM)

The TPRM is a peer review procedure, with its mandate set out in the Agreement establishing the WTO.³⁷ It allows for frequent examination of trade policies of member

³² MT Ladan, *Materials and Cases on Public International Law* (Ahmadu Bello University Press 2007) 893.

³³ Smriti Chand, (n. 13)

³⁴ Malenbakeng Agnes Forere, (n. 6) 41.

³⁵ Article IV of the WTO Agreement.

³⁶ PV Bossche, *The Law, and Policy of World Trade Organization: Texts, Cases and Materials* (Cambridge University Press 2005) 3

³⁷ Annex 3 to the Marrakash Agreement

states, depending on their share of the world economy. It is mandatory that each member gives details of its numerous trade dealings to the WTO, which in turn preserve in a large data base.³⁸

The purpose of the TPRM is to enhance honesty and openness to achieve better understanding of the economic policies that each member country is pursuing, and to assess their impact, and advise, where necessary. It is important that all WTO member countries undertake this periodic examination by the WTO and each evaluation must contain reports of the country under review. The merit of the examination is to assist in the improvement of observance of rules, disciplines and obligations made by members under the multilateral and plurilateral trading arrangements to achieve better coherence.³⁹

TPRM therefore, creates a forum for WTO members to deliberate and decide on liberal tariff reductions to improve standards of living and ultimately achieve sustainable economic development. It also assists developing countries, with over three quarters of WTO membership in their trade policy issues, through technical assistance and training programmes.⁴⁰ However, while some WTO members view the trade policy reviews as positive criticism on their policies, others view it as restricting their rights to make policies that best suits their economic circumstances.

2.7 WTO Dispute Settlement Mechanism

The Dispute Settlement System (DSS) of the WTO incorporates the DSB, the Dispute Settlement Panels (DSP) and the Appellate Body (AB). While the DSB is viewed as an administrative organization within the framework of the WTO, the DSP and AB are viewed as judicial institutions,⁴¹ with original and appellate jurisdictions, respectively. Under the WTO law, all members are subject to the DSB without any reservations. As provided for in the DSU, the DSB has both compulsory and exclusive authority to determine trade disagreements concerning WTO members on trade matters resulting from the Marrakesh Agreement. The subject matter includes goods, agriculture, sanitary, textile and clothing, barriers to trade, investment measures, rules of origin,

³⁸Ay res Thomas Banwell, (n. 12)

³⁹ Smriti Chand, (n. 13)

⁴⁰ PV Bossche, (n. 32), 124.

⁴¹ MT Ladan (n. 28) 378.

import licensing procedure, subsidies and countervailing measures, safeguards, services, IP, and dispute settlement.⁴²

To this end the WTO performs the following functions:

- i. supervises the procedure for dialogue between members in trade disputes.
- ii. appoints panels to resolve trade issues.
- iii. accepts or rejects panel or appellate bodies' recommendations.
- iv. follow-up on the enforcement of rulings and recommendations; and
- v. authorizes retaliation where recommendations are not observed.

It must be noted that a trade dispute arises where a member country implements certain trade strategy or measures that another or other members deems inconsistent with the WTO agreements. Essentially, trade disagreements in the WTO border on broken promises by member countries. To this end, WTO members have unanimously resolved that if a fellow member violates any trade provisions, the multilateral procedure for resolving issues must be utilized, rather than unilateral action. Thus, the trade dispute settlement procedure is more of legal than diplomatic process and more of ruled-based than power-based procedure.⁴³

There are three types of trade disagreements that can be initiated before the WTO-DSB. These are:

- i. Violation complaints - This requires overriding or losing a benefit because of the inability of another member country to fulfil its WTO obligations.
- ii. Non-violation complaints - A member can go to the DSB even when a WTO agreement has not been violated.
- iii. Situation complaints – This covers any situation, whatsoever if it results in overriding or losing of benefits.⁴⁴

However, trade disputes among WTO member countries can be resolved by any of the following devices:⁴⁵

- i. Consultation/Negotiation

Where there is a breach of obligation under a WTO agreement and a member desire to dialogue with another member, the latter member must agree to negotiate with the

⁴² A Narlikar (*n. 21*) 88.

⁴³ LN Anyiwe and EO Ekhaton, 'Developing Countries and the WTO Dispute Resolution System: A Legal Assessment and Review' Afe Babalola University, *Journal of Sustainable Development Law, and Policy*, (2013) (2)(1) 117.

⁴⁴ A Narlikar, (*n. 21*) 88

⁴⁵ Article 2.1 of Dispute Settlement Body

former in 30 days. Where the trade disagreement is not resolved in 60 days, the complaining member may request that a panel be constituted for that purpose.

ii. Good offices, Conciliation and Mediation

This process is initiated where the disputing parties agree to it. Due to their voluntary nature, the proceedings and the position arrived at by the parties enjoy some degree of confidentiality and without prejudice to their rights in further proceedings.

iii. Arbitration

Arbitration is the most appropriate means of resolving trade disagreements where issues to be determined are well-defined by both parties. In this regard, parties are allowed to appoint arbitrators or, if they fail to agree on the appointment of a certain arbitrator, it is within the discretionary powers of the Director-General to appoint one for the parties.

iv. Adjudication by Panels and the Appellate Body

The request to constitute a panel and AB must be made in writing; identifying the precise measures on the issue, with a brief and clear description of the complaint that is adequate to present the crisis. Once it is duly constituted, the panel will proceed to hear both oral and written arguments from the parties, and after a careful deliberation of the arguments presented before it, the panel will issue a descriptive part of its report (facts and argument) to the parties. A final report is usually issued to the parties in the trade dispute and subsequently copied to all WTO Member countries, after a period of review.⁴⁶

2.8 Enforcement of Recommendations Adopted by the DSB and AB

If the DSB finds a defending member in violation of WTO obligations, such member is expected to inform the DSB on how it plans to implement the recommendations adopted by the DSB within 30 days after the panel report and any AB report that its adopted. Where it is not feasible to timely fulfil the recommendation of the panel, the member can do so within a reasonable period. Where the offending member fails to adopt corrective measures within a reasonable period, the DSU⁴⁷ provides that the disputing parties should negotiate compensation for the aggrieved party and in the absence of agreement on this compensation, the DSB can approve retaliation.⁴⁸

⁴⁶ D Collins, *The World Trade Organisation: A Beginner's Guide* (London One world Publications 2015) 43

⁴⁷ Article XXII 2

⁴⁸ MT Ladan, (n. 28), 302.

The WTO's method of determining trade disagreements under the DSU is vital for enforcing the rules and ensuring that trade strives efficiently. Member countries initiate trade disputes proceedings in the WTO where their rights as stipulated in the agreements are being or likely to be infringed. Usually, specially chosen independent experts are appointed and their decisions flow from the clarifications of the agreements and member countries' obligations. The aim is to encourage members to reconcile their differences by consultation through the DSB. In the likely event that it fails, parties can opt for possible ruling by the DSP and the chance to appeal the ruling on legal grounds to the AB.⁴⁹

However, there is no general answer as to whether the WTO dispute settlement process has been effective in resolving the trade disagreements involving developing countries and LDCs. So far, only four African member States (Benin, Côte d'Ivoire, Senegal, and Nigeria) have participated in a few WTO disputes as third parties, even though developing countries consists of three-quarter of members in the WTO.⁵⁰ While some experts are of the view that the DSU has failed developing countries and LDCs, other experts are of the opinion that developing countries and LDCs have immensely benefited from its participation in WTO-DSU mechanisms.⁵¹

3.0 CHALLENGES FOR NIGERIA AS DEVELOPING COUNTRY MEMBER OF THE WTO

Like any other developing country member nation, Nigeria's membership and participation in the WTO is not devoid of challenges. Some of the challenges identified are discussed below:

i. Foreign Aids

Nigeria's dependent on foreign financial aids has so much influence on its international trade policies against developed countries, who are most likely its trading partners, particularly where these partners are the major financial aid donors, investors, or former colonial masters. In this regard, Nigeria faces four main economic challenges; reduction of domestic savings and investment in favour of greater consumption; inflation; diminishing exports; and difficulty in absorbing such large

⁴⁹ Smriti Chand, (n. 13)

⁵⁰ ECOWAS to Hold Workshop on WTO Dispute Settlement System', <<http://www.ecowas.int/ecowas-to-hold-workshop-on-wto-dispute-settlement-system/>> accessed on 7 November 2023

⁵¹ Jan Bohanes and Garza Fernanda, 'Going Beyond Stereotypes: Participation of Developing Countries in the WTO Dispute Settlement' Trade, Law, and Development (2012) (1) (1) 45.

cash influxes. Thus, as foreign aids come in, domestic savings decline, and investment invariably falls.⁵²

Since the 1990s many foreign aid sources to Nigeria, notably the IMF, have made aid conditional on market-oriented economic reforms, such as structural adjustment programme (SAP), lowering trade barriers, devaluation of currency and privatization. Thus, foreign aid has been used as a tool by some institutions and countries to encourage the spread of capitalism. It has been viewed suspiciously as nothing more than a tool of influence of donor countries. For example, critics of the IMF alleged that the debts incurred through its loans help to create poverty in Nigeria, as capital that could have been invested instead was channeled into debt repayment.⁵³

ii. The Principle of Non-Discrimination

Some of the agreements of the WTO on trade in goods and services as well as IPRs have led to limited access to food and healthcare, particularly with regards to strict adherence to the MFN and NT principles. While the basic rationale for the principle of non-discrimination appears to be straightforward, the application of the different legal elements which constitute its obligation has proven to be most challenging. Adjudicating bodies have been applying different interpretations and standards regarding the legal elements of 'less favourable treatment', 'likeness' and 'regulatory purpose', which leads to a high fragmentation of the non-discrimination principle in global economic integration.⁵⁴

It has been argued that rather than the principle of non-discrimination protecting Nigeria, it takes undue advantage of the country's manufacturing incapacities.⁵⁵ For instance, the activities of oil multinational corporations (MNCs) in Nigeria have been at the centre of scandals regarding poor labour standards, environmental degradation, and human rights violations, amongst others.⁵⁶

iii. High Profile Corruption

⁵² Dambisa Moyo, 'DEAD AID: Why Aid is not Working and How There is a Better Way for Africa' (New York Faqrar Straus and Giroux 2009) 60.

⁵³ V Williams, 'Foreign Aid' <<https://www.britannica.com/money/foreign-aid>> accessed 19 March 2024

⁵⁴ NF Diebold, 'Standards of Non-Discrimination in International Economic Law' *International and Comparative Law Quarterly* (2011) (60)4.

⁵⁵ Markus Krajewski, 'General Agreement on Trade in Services 1994' <<https://opil.ouplaw.com/display/10.1093/law:epil/9780199231690/law-9780199231690-e1527>> accessed 2 October 2023.

⁵⁶ Eghosa O Ekhatior, 'Regulating the Activities of Oil Multinationals in Nigeria: A Case for Self-Regulation?' *Journal of African Law* (2015) (60) 1.

Nigeria is characterized by porous borders that are fraught with corrupt customs officials, who habitually violates custom rules on daily basis. For instance, Nigeria's trade policy on import prohibition of foreign rice to protect local industries was overwhelmed by high-profiled smuggling and corruption.⁵⁷

Some of the reasons adduced for the prevalence of corruption in Nigeria includes weak government institutions and poverty. Well-connected businesspeople gain from anti-competitive practices that reduce market forces. However, the Nigerian government has sought to address corruption through the establishment of anti-corruption agencies like; the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC), and the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (EITI). Unfortunately, cases progressing to conviction are rare.⁵⁸

iv. Legal and Institutional Decay

Another challenge for Nigeria is lack of standard legal and institutional framework, and policy inconsistencies. Nigeria's trade laws are obsolete, and the policies and institutions have overlapping functions, with multiplicity of responsibilities. Related to this, is political instability and rampant military intervention in politics that may result in policy modification without notice. Prospective investors would not risk investing their monies in an unpredictable legal environment.⁵⁹

Other set of challenges retarding Nigeria's international trade development are violations of IPRs laws that continue to be widespread due to inadequate enforcement that stems from insufficient resources among enforcement agencies. Thus, the Nigerian economy has more to lose than ever from inadequate IPRs protections, including online digital piracy.⁶⁰ However, the Local Content Law,⁶¹ originally introduced to ensure local participation across the value chain of the oil and gas sector have gradually begun to spread to other sectors such as Information and Communications Technology (ICT).

v. Trade Barriers

⁵⁷ Jan Bohanes and Garza Fernanda, (n. 47)

⁵⁸ International Trade Association, 'Nigeria – Country Commercial Guide' < <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/nigeria-market-challenges>> accessed 19 March 2024.

⁵⁹ Smriti Chand, (n. 13)

⁶⁰ International Trade Association, (n. 54)

⁶¹ 2010

Unfortunately, trade barriers are land mines that pose significant challenges for investors and exporters. In a bid to protect local industries from highly competitive imports, Nigeria has employed several import substitution policies which aim to increase local production over imports through subsidies, tariffs, quotas, restrict or place bans on certain imports and other barriers to trade. Amongst these measures is the Government directive which stipulates that preference be granted to domestic manufacturers, contractors, and service providers in all government procurements. This directive⁶² states that at least 40% of expenditure for the procurement of the following items shall be on locally manufactured goods: Uniforms and footwear, food and beverages, furniture and fittings, stationery, motor vehicles, pharmaceuticals, construction materials and information technology.⁶³

While these policies are intended to boost domestic production, when critically examined, they are barriers that impede international trade. With its large population and abundant natural resources, Nigeria offers an attractive market for investors and traders. However, Nigeria is yet to witness the desired level of economic growth and is vigorously seeking to attract foreign investment commensurate with its immense economic potentials.⁶⁴

v. **WTO Decision Making**

Decision making at the WTO fora are done unilaterally by way of consensus-building that engaged small group of countries, predominantly developed countries, while the rest of the countries were relatively passive. Nigeria as a developing country member and major importer of traded goods does not have adequate competences to participate in the WTO discussions on negotiations.⁶⁵ Therefore, it had to accept obligations developed by consensus at the WTO decision, which requires its implementation and enforcement of regulatory policies with great difficulty in fulfilling, as well as, commit to substantially greater reforms of its trade barriers and trade practices than it did in the past. However, it is suggested that the country needs to be better informed about issues under negotiation since it has a greater stake in the

⁶² Issued via an Executive Order in May 2017.

⁶³ Export.Gov, 'Nigeria-Trade Barriers' <<https://www.export.gov/apex/article2?id=Nigeria-Trade-Barriers>> accessed 18 March 2024

⁶⁴ Adebayo Adeleke, 'Importance of removing trade barriers for Nigerian investors and exporters' Business Day December 27, 2023

⁶⁵ MT Ladan, (n. 28) 402

world trading system and a better claim on participation in the WTO's decision-making process due to its market size.⁶⁶

vi. Trade Policy Review Mechanisms

The WTO's periodic review of members' trade policies is another challenge for Nigeria. Most often, the report of the review tends to be superficial and uncritical. TPRs should aim at influencing domestic politics, help juxtapose trade policies across countries and reflects the economic circumstances of Nigeria, particularly its predominant informal economy. Besides, the procedure for TPRs should be improved and the drafting of the Secretariat's report should allow for greater stakeholder participation.⁶⁷

However, the United States (US) was quick to criticize Nigeria's trade policies in the oil and gas industry and urge the country to renew its efforts to reform its trade policies. According to the US, Nigeria's apparent departure from the open and market-based approach to development and continues use of restrictive trade measures, nontransparent valuation procedures, and nontransparent laws and regulations would deleteriously affect trade and investment in Nigeria's critically important oil and gas industry. The US encouraged Nigeria to undertake trade policies that support its goals to strengthen its economic well-being, including diversification, increased private investment, and strengthened the agricultural sector.⁶⁸

viii. Disputes Settlement Mechanism

Nigeria finds real challenges with the current dispute settlement mechanisms due to lack of adequate know-how in the WTO law, helplessness in the enforcement of DSU rulings, unwillingness to institute trade disputes because of political and economic pressures likely to be visited on it by developed countries. Thus, the practical effectiveness of the dispute settlement procedure, regarding Nigeria has been a matter of contention.⁶⁹

Between 1980 and 1991, at least three countries lodged formal complaints against Nigeria with respect to import prohibitions: Norway submitted a complaint on

⁶⁶ JJ Scott and J Watal, *Decision-making in the WTO*, (2000), <<https://www.piie.com/publications/policy-briefs/decision-making-wto>> accessed 18 March 2024.

⁶⁷ Valentin Zahrnt, *The WTO's Trade Policy Review Mechanism: How to Create Political Will for Liberalization?* ECIPE WORKING PAPER (2009) 11.

⁶⁸ US Mission to International Organisations in Geneva, 'WTO Trade Policy Review of Nigeria' <<https://geneva.usmission.gov/2011/06/28/tpr-nigeria/>> accessed 18 March 2024

⁶⁹ Gregory C Shaffer, *The Challenges of WTO Law: Strategies for Developing Country Adaptation* *WORLD TRADE REV.* (2006) (177)5.

Nigeria's import ban on stockfish, Côte d'Ivoire on the import ban on textiles, and the US on the import ban on wheat and rice. While both Norway and the US cited violation of GATT rules in their complaints, Côte d'Ivoire's case rested on a violation of the ECOWAS treaty. These complaints were settled through bilateral negotiation and consultation. More recently, both the European Union (EU) and Benin have raised issues with Nigeria regarding its import prohibitions. The EU argued that Nigeria's import ban was not compatible with, and indeed forbidden by WTO rules. On its part, Benin Republic argued that Nigeria's import bans, particularly on textile products, had dealt a severe blow to its economy and 'constituted a violation of the Memorandum of Understanding between the two countries regarding continuous trade liberalization.'⁷⁰ However, the medium of settling investment disputes under an investment code or treaty is as important as the protection of trade and investment in Nigeria. The Nigeria Investment Promotion Commission (NIPC) Act⁷¹ is instructive with regards to the mode of settlement of investment disputes in Nigeria. It states:

(1) Where a dispute arises between an investor and any Government of the Federation in respect of an enterprise, all efforts shall be made through mutual discussion to reach an amicable settlement.

(2) Any dispute between an investor and any Government of the Federation in respect of an enterprise to which this Act applies which is not amicably settled through mutual discussions, may be submitted at the option of the aggrieved party to arbitration as follows.

(a) In the case of a Nigerian investor, in accordance with the rules of procedure for arbitration as specified in the Arbitration and Conciliation Act; or

(b) In the case of a foreign investor, within the framework of any bilateral or multilateral agreement on investment protection to which the Federal Government and the country of which the investor is a national are parties; or

(c) In accordance with any other national or international machinery for the settlement of investment disputes agreed on by the parties.

(3) Where in respect of any dispute, there is disagreement between the investor and the Federal Government as to the method of dispute settlement to be

⁷⁰ Ademola Oyejide, A. Ogunkola and A. Bankole, 'Import Prohibition as a Trade Policy Instruments: The Nigerian Experience'

<https://www.wto.org/english/res_e/booksp_e/casestudies_e/case32_e.htm#:~:text=Against%20these%20opostulated%20positive%20outcomes,tariff%20revenue%20and%20creating%20veste> accessed 4 March 2024

⁷¹ S. 26

adopted, the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes Rules shall apply.

In view of the above, a framework on how disputes which arise out of trade agreements or FDI will be resolved will instill a level of confidence in the Nigerian market wherein an investor can settle any trade or commercial transaction related disputes In line with international best practices.

ix. Trade Liberalization

The purpose of the WTO is to enable trade liberalization in goods and services, but trade liberalization does not necessarily imply fair trade as it increases discrimination and widens the gap between member countries. The global trading system as canvassed by the WTO is unable to recognize this hostile effect of free trade on the standards of justice.⁷² In addition, free trade can only be beneficial to developed economies with massive MNCs and lots of capital that once they enter into Nigeria's market, hampers the business of local traders and businessmen, and removes the competition, thereby making the country's economy dependent on the foreign companies.⁷³

Under the Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry Content Development Act of 2010, Nigerian independent operators are given first consideration in the award of oil projects in Nigeria. In addition, MNCs working through Nigerian subsidiaries must demonstrate that a minimum of 50% of the equipment used is owned by Nigerian subsidiaries.⁷⁴

4.0 PROSPECTS FOR NIGERIA IN THE WTO

Membership and involvement of Nigeria in the WTO comes along with certain rights and corresponding obligations, thus, there are potential prospects for the country in the WTO.

i. Special and Differential Treatment (SDT) Provision

The Agreements establishing the WTO provides developing member countries and LDCs with longer transition periods before they are fully required to implement the agreement. There is also special and differential treatment (SDT) provision for

⁷² International trade Association (n. 54)

⁷³ Mohan Kumar, 'Negotiation Dynamics of the WTO: An Insider Account' <<https://books.google.com.ng/books?id=YpWDwAAQBAJ&pg=PA17&lpg=PA17&dq=Kumar,+H.+%E2%80%98What+are+the+Objectives+of+the+WTO&source=bl&ots=meDb7LQUir&sig=ACfU3U2FcLx9Pgi1rIl6F5G3VcTvD4DYEg&hl=en&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwjiwtixm5KDAxUgRkEAHbyGAoo4FBD0AXoECAUQA#v=onepage&q=Kumar%2C%20H.%20%E2%80%98What%20are%20the%20Objectives%20of%20the%20WTO&f=false>> accessed 5 October 2023

⁷⁴ International Trade Administration (n. 54)

developing countries and LDCs because of the circumstances and level of their developments, as well as provision of technical assistance for them by the developed countries.⁷⁵ Nigeria can benefit from that if properly utilized.

ii. Market Access

Looking at the multilateral trade regimes, Nigeria as member of the WTO can benefit from the new rules and disciplines agreed upon in the Uruguay Round regarding both access to the developed markets, and the transparency and certainty of their trade regimes.⁷⁶ To gain seeming advantage of the opportunities of global economic integration through trade, Nigeria have granted developed countries access to its market. Free trade in agriculture and labour-intensive products would assist Nigeria move away from abject poverty while it also benefits rich countries to market their industrial goods.⁷⁷

iii. Effective Regulatory Framework

The deepening and expansion of global trade agreements would widen the scope of trade opportunities for Nigeria's businesses. The country has the potential of becoming more competitive player in the global trade. However, there is the need to initiate intervention measures with the aim of improving the business climate in terms of a conducive regulatory regime that would guarantee access to finance and infrastructural development.⁷⁸

iv. Trade Liberalization

Trade liberalization has the potential benefits for Nigeria since it can ill-afford subsidies, often directed to certain interests' domestic companies, that protectionism offers, besides, the augmented development that trade liberalization provides; creating employment opportunities, raising standard of living, and thus filling the existing gaps created by inequalities within and outside the WTO member countries.

v. Dispute Resolution Mechanism

The WTO has played a vital role in shaping and promoting international trade and reducing tensions in international relations which often contribute to wars, because of

⁷⁵ Kwa Aileen, 'Power and Politics in the WTO' <<http://www.aftinet.org.au/papers/kwa1.html>> accessed 10 August 2023

⁷⁶ IMF, 'Global Trade Liberalization and Developing Countries' <<https://www.imf.org/external/np/exr/ib/2001/110801.htm>> accessed 10 October 2023.

⁷⁷ Rupa Chanda, 'GATT and Its Implications Developing Countries: Key Issues and Concerns' DESA Discussion Paper (2002)(25) 2.

⁷⁸ Republic of Kenya, 'National Trade Policy: Efficient Globally Competitive Economy' (2009) 11.

its trade dispute resolution mechanisms and has introduced and sustained certain level of self-control in international trade because of its sanctions. To this end, the WTO has provided the forum for Nigeria to participate in world economic arena and to compete the quality of its goods and services with those of other member countries, apart from strengthening economic relationship amongst them.⁷⁹

5.0 CONCLUSION

There is no doubt that the WTO has played a momentous part in packaging international trade as an object for fostering better development objectives for all the member countries, but its effect varies from country to country, even within the class of developed countries because of different economic circumstances. However, various damaging features relating to the structure, processes and dealings of the WTO are identified.

The non-discrimination principle on traded goods undermines the role of the WTO, since goods produced in an informal developing economy, like Nigeria cannot adequately compete with equally tariffed goods produced by MNCs of developed economy, which often rely on cheap human labour to lower their costs of production. Although this would seem a barrier to trade liberalization, a better and up-to-date function of the WTO in protecting commercial interest of all member countries, irrespective of their economic development would assist the organization accomplish its professed objectives of improved standards of living and employment opportunities anchored on sustainable development.

Juxtaposing the DSS of the WTO with other similar international organizations, the WTO can be said to be a success. However, most of the members' participation in the dispute settlement process has been negligible, as very few developing countries-initiated trade disagreements under the DSU. Until Nigeria and other developing countries in the WTO record improved involvement in the trade disagreement, the DSU and DSM should not be measured as being a success. Overall, the much-acclaimed DSS should be seen as protecting the interests of developed member countries at the detriment of developing member countries.

Despite the many years of foreign aid provided by affluent nations to Nigeria, it is ineffective at assisting the country in achieve its developmental objectives. Reforming

⁷⁹ Kwa Aileen (n. 71)

the dynamics of foreign aid is necessary in Nigeria. This can be done by fixing inherent structural lapses such as corruption and institutional failures in the country.

The Doha, Bali and Abu Dhabi Round negotiations has changed from the declared path-oriented to a market access path-oriented, with Nigeria under intense pressure to open up market access of their agricultural and services sectors. The WTO has also been unsuccessful in substantiating the deliberate trade rules that tolerate the manipulations of developing countries by the developed countries. For instance, in trade negotiations with the EU, developing countries were involuntary made to remove tariffs because there are no clear rules in existence for their protection.

1. To motivate and sustain the assurances for Nigeria as equal stakeholder in the global trade negotiations, the WTO must not only be transparent, but it must be seen to be credible, unbiased, and just to all its signatories. The SDT rules for developing countries and LDCs should be more specific, effective, and functioning to fill the legal vacuum. It is however hopeful that the WTO will emerge as an effective enabler of impending trade negotiations in the succeeding years.